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An Effective Broad-Spectrum Antimicrobial Against Bacterial and Fungal Pathogens with Clinical Applications in Autoimmune Diseases

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ABSTRACT

Oregano oil is renowned for its potent antimicrobial properties with a historical record of diverse uses dating back over 3000 years. In this study, we investigated the antimicrobial potential of oregano oil against a panel of bacterial and fungal pathogens, including *Staphylococcus coagulase-negative*, *S. aureus*, *Enterococcus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Candida albicans*, and *Aspergillus*. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing revealed that oregano oil elicited a zone of inhibition against all tested microorganisms, with varying degrees of sensitivity observed among the strains. Notably, certain strains exhibited heightened sensitivity to oregano oil, indicating its potential as a broad-spectrum bacteriostatic, bactericidal, and antifungal agent in laboratory settings. Leaky gut syndrome often improves with an anti-inflammatory diet, but in cases of SIBO or SIFO (small intestinal bacterial or fungal overgrowth) pose challenges that require herbal antimicrobials like oregano oil. Given the escalating global challenge of antimicrobial resistance, conventional antimicrobials face increasing limitations. Oregano oil emerges as a promising alternative for combating infections caused by resistant pathogens. Its ability to inhibit the growth of clinically relevant bacteria and fungi highlights its therapeutic potential in addressing multidrug resistant infections in clinical settings. This study provides compelling evidence supporting the effectiveness of oregano oil as a powerful antimicrobial agent against a diverse range of bacteria and fungi that have been known to induce autoimmune diseases in patients. Its historical use combined with contemporary findings in the field of integrative functional medicine underscores its value as a potential therapeutic tool in the battle against chronic and antibiotic-resistant infections.

INTRODUCTION

Infections have been a longstanding challenge to human health, constituting a prevalent source of disease processes worldwide. The global burden of infectious diseases has shaped medical practices, leading to the extensive use of conventional antibiotics. However, the excessive use of these antibiotics has fueled the emergence of multiresistant microbial strains, rendering current treatments ineffective against many common pathogens. The rise of multidrug-resistant bacteria has become a critical concern for healthcare facilities globally, as they pose significant challenges to infection control and patient care.

According to hospital and world statistics, the prevalence of multiresistant bacteria continues to increase, with infections caused by these microbes being associated with higher morbidity, mortality, and healthcare costs [1]. The need for alternative approaches to combat antimicrobial resistance has never been more pressing.

Oregano oil has a long history of medicinal use, dating back to ancient civilizations such as the Greeks, Romans, and Egyptians [2]. It was valued for its potential healing properties and was used to treat various ailments, including respiratory and digestive issues. Traditional Chinese medicine and indigenous cultures across different continents also incorporated oregano oil into their remedies for promoting good health and addressing specific health concerns [3].

During the Middle Ages and in the Mediterranean region, oregano continued to be used as a part of traditional folk medicine. It was believed to have the power to ward off illnesses and was commonly used in herbal remedies and tonics. Throughout history, it has been recognized for its diverse applications and its potent ability to combat infections [4]. Recent scientific studies have shed light on the unique properties exhibited by oregano oil that contribute to its antimicrobial efficacy.

Oregano Oil is derived from the *Origanum vulgare* plant, commonly known as wild marjoram. The main chemical compounds found in oregano oil responsible for its antimicrobial properties include carvacrol, thymol, p-cymene, and γ-terpinene [5]. These active constituents have demonstrated remarkable bacteriostatic, bactericidal, and antifungal activities against a wide range of pathogenic microorganisms, including drug-resistant strains [5].

The versatility of oregano oil makes it a highly promising candidate in the ongoing battle against multiresistant microbes. As the efficacy of conventional antibiotics wanes, exploring alternative or adjunct therapeutic options becomes imperative to address the mounting challenges of increasingly difficult-to-treat infections.

Oregano oil has gained recognition within the field of integrative functional medicine, where conditions like SIBO (Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth) and SIFO (Small Intestinal Fungal Overgrowth) demand the use of herbal antimicrobials [6].

Integrative functional health care providers have turned to oregano oil as a viable alternative for treating such conditions, given its notable antimicrobial properties and a generally excellent safety profile [7]. The use of oregano oil in these contexts has gained popularity due to its potential to effectively combat pathogenic overgrowth without causing significant harm to the beneficial gut microbiota [8].

In the present study, we sought to assess the efficacy of oregano oil against a panel of relevant bacterial and fungal strains, including *Staphylococcus coagulase-negative*, *S. aureus*, *Enterococcus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Candida albicans*, and *Aspergillus*. Employing antimicrobial susceptibility testing, we observed a zone of inhibition in response to oregano oil against all tested microorganisms, albeit with varying degrees of sensitivity among the strains. Particularly noteworthy was the heightened sensitivity displayed by certain strains, indicating the potential of oregano oil as a broad-spectrum antimicrobial agent with bacteriostatic, bactericidal, and antifungal properties, as observed in laboratory settings.

As we face the daunting challenge of antimicrobial resistance, oregano oil emerges as a valuable tool in the fight against treatment-resistant infections [9]. With its established antimicrobial activity against a range of pathogens and its positive clinical outcomes, oregano oil represents a promising natural alternative to conventional antibiotics and warrants further exploration as an integral part of integrative functional medicine approaches to combatting microbial dysbiosis and infections thus offering a glimpse of hope in the pursuit of more sustainable and effective therapeutic strategies in different clinical and hospital scenarios.

CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF OREGANO OIL

Oregano oil is derived from the leaves of the oregano plant (*Origanum vulgare* or *Origanum heracleoticum*) through a steam distillation process. It is known for its strong aromatic and flavorful characteristics and has been used for culinary and medicinal purposes for centuries. The chemical properties of oregano oil are primarily attributed to its active compounds, which contribute to its antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties [10].

Below are the key chemical properties of oregano oil:

Main Chemical Constituents:

Oregano oil is rich in various bioactive compounds, including phenols, terpenes, and flavonoids. The primary constituents responsible for its medicinal properties include [11]:

Phenols: Carvacrol and thymol are the major phenolic compounds found in oregano oil. Carvacrol is the most potent and is responsible for the majority of its antimicrobial activity [11].

Terpenes: Beta-caryophyllene and thymol are terpenes found in oregano oil that contribute to its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects [11].

Flavonoids: Apigenin and luteolin are two flavonoids present in oregano oil, which also contribute to its antioxidant properties [11].

Antimicrobial Properties:

Oregano oil is known for its potent antimicrobial activity against a wide range of bacteria, fungi, and parasites. Carvacrol and thymol are the main compounds responsible for this activity. They disrupt the cell membranes of microorganisms, leading to their destruction and inhibiting their growth. Oregano oil has been studied for its efficacy against bacterial strains, including *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Salmonella* species, as well as fungal pathogens such as *Candida albicans* [12].

Antioxidant Activity:

The phenolic compounds in oregano oil, especially carvacrol and thymol, possess strong antioxidant properties. These compounds scavenge free radicals and reactive oxygen species, helping to protect cells from oxidative damage and reducing oxidative stress in the body [13].

Anti-inflammatory Effects:

Oregano oil's terpenes, particularly beta-caryophyllene, exhibit anti-inflammatory properties by inhibiting pro-inflammatory enzymes and cytokines. This can help in reducing inflammation associated with various conditions, including arthritis and inflammatory bowel disease [13].

Other Health Benefits:

Oregano oil has been studied for potential benefits in various health conditions, including its role in supporting the immune system, promoting digestive health, and providing relief from respiratory ailments [13].

Volatility and Stability:

Oregano oil is volatile, meaning it easily evaporates at room temperature. Proper storage in a cool, dark place, away from direct sunlight, can help maintain its chemical stability and potency [13].

ANTIMICROBIAL PROPERTIES: (CARVACROL & THYMOL)

Carvacrol and Thymol are two potent phenolic compounds found in oregano oil, and they play a crucial role in its antimicrobial activity against bacteria, fungi, parasites, and viruses. Let's explore how these compounds act on specific structures within these microorganisms:

Bacteria:

Carvacrol and Thymol exert their antimicrobial effects on bacteria through several mechanisms:

Cell Membrane Disruption:

The bacterial cell membrane serves as a critical barrier, maintaining cell integrity and controlling the transport of substances into and out of the cell. Carvacrol and Thymol, being lipophilic compounds, effortlessly penetrate the bacterial cell membrane due to their structural resemblance to fatty acids within the membrane [14].

Once inside, Carvacrol and Thymol interact with the lipid bilayer, inducing structural disruptions. These phenolic compounds cause disorder in lipid arrangement, resulting in the destabilization of the membrane. Consequently, the cell membrane becomes more permeable, leading to the leakage of essential ions and molecules from the bacterial cell. This disruption of cellular homeostasis and processes ultimately culminates in bacterial cell death [14].

Additionally, Carvacrol and Thymol specifically target proteins and enzymes embedded in the bacterial cell membrane. By interfering with the function of transporters and receptors, these phenolic compounds further compromise the normal functioning of the bacterium, exacerbating the damage to the cell membrane [14].

Protein Denaturation:

In bacterial cells, proteins are vital macromolecules responsible for various functions, including enzymatic reactions, structural support, and cell signaling. Carvacrol and Thymol interact with specific amino acid residues within these proteins through hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions [14].

Upon interaction, Carvacrol and Thymol induce conformational changes in bacterial proteins, leading to protein denaturation. This process involves the disruption of the protein's secondary, tertiary, and quaternary structures, causing the loss of its functional shape and activity [14].

For instance, enzymes are crucial for bacterial metabolism and growth. By denaturing these enzymes, Carvacrol and Thymol effectively inhibit essential cellular processes, such as energy production and cell wall synthesis. This interference ultimately impedes bacterial growth and replication [14].

Antioxidant Effects:

Both Carvacrol and Thymol exhibit potent antioxidant properties by donating hydrogen atoms to free radicals and reactive oxygen species (ROS). These unstable molecules can inflict oxidative damage to various cellular components, including proteins, lipids, and nucleic acids [15].

By scavenging and neutralizing free radicals and ROS, Carvacrol and Thymol protect bacterial cells from oxidative stress. Oxidative stress can be detrimental to bacteria and may lead to cell damage and death. Hence, the antioxidant effects of Carvacrol and Thymol not only directly contribute to bacterial cell death but also enhance the overall efficacy of oregano oil as a powerful antimicrobial agent [15].

In summary, the effectiveness of oregano oil against bacteria can be attributed to the multifaceted mechanisms of its main phenolic compounds, Carvacrol and Thymol. Through cell membrane disruption, protein denaturation, and antioxidant effects, oregano oil disrupts crucial bacterial structures and processes, ultimately leading to bacterial cell death and the elimination of bacterial infections. These combined actions highlight oregano oil as a promising natural alternative for combating bacterial pathogens and hold potential for reducing the risk of antibiotic resistance.

Fungi:

Carvacrol and Thymol are effective against various fungal species through similar mechanisms as observed in bacteria:

Cell Membrane Disruption:

Oregano oil demonstrates its remarkable efficacy against bacteria through the potent mechanism of cell membrane disruption. Bacterial cell membranes play a pivotal role in maintaining cellular integrity and regulating molecular transport. Central to this antimicrobial activity are the key bioactive compounds found in oregano oil, specifically Carvacrol and Thymol, which exhibit lipophilic properties. These compounds possess a structural resemblance to fatty acids present in the bacterial cell membrane, enabling them to readily traverse the membrane [12].

Upon penetrating the bacterial cell, Carvacrol and Thymol initiate interactions with the lipid bilayer, leading to structural perturbations. These phenolic compounds induce disorganization in the arrangement of lipids, resulting in the destabilization of the cell membrane. As a consequence, the membrane's permeability increases, facilitating the leakage of essential ions and molecules from the bacterial cell. This disruption of cell membrane integrity leads to a loss of cellular content, causing the collapse of cellular homeostasis, ultimately culminating in bacterial cell death [12].

Furthermore, Carvacrol and Thymol exhibit a remarkable ability to selectively target specific proteins and enzymes embedded within the bacterial cell membrane.

By interfering with the function of these critical proteins, such as transporters and receptors, these phenolic compounds further exacerbate the disruption of normal cellular functioning. This exquisite mode of action amplifies the damage inflicted upon the bacterial cell membrane, ensuring effective eradication of the bacteria [12].

Inhibition of Fungal Enzymes:

In the context of fungal infections, the effectiveness of oregano oil extends to the inhibition of vital fungal enzymes. Fungal cells rely on an array of enzymes crucial for various metabolic pathways and essential cellular processes. Carvacrol and Thymol, the prominent constituents of oregano oil, engage in specific interactions with amino acid residues within these enzymes, facilitated by hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions [16].

As a consequence of these interactions, Carvacrol and Thymol induce profound conformational changes in fungal enzymes, leading to their denaturation. This disruptive process involves altering the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary structures of these enzymes, resulting in the loss of their functional shapes and activities [16].

Significantly, certain fungal enzymes hold pivotal roles in essential processes such as cell wall synthesis and energy production. By effectively inhibiting these enzymes, Carvacrol and Thymol profoundly impede vital cellular processes, effectively arresting fungal growth and replication [16].

Fungal Spore Inhibition:

A notable aspect of oregano oil's antifungal activity lies in its ability to effectively inhibit fungal spores. Fungal spores serve as the reproductive units of fungi, playing a pivotal role in the dissemination and persistence of fungal infections. Carvacrol and Thymol, acting upon the germination process of fungal spores, have demonstrated their ability to interfere with this crucial stage of fungal life cycle [17].

Upon exposure to oregano oil, the germination of fungal spores is effectively impeded, preventing the development of new fungal cells. By arresting the germination process, oregano oil significantly curtails the dissemination of fungal infections and restricts the establishment of new colonies [17].

BENEFITS & CLINICAL APPLICATION OF OREGANO OIL: In the management of SIBO, SIFO and Biofilms

In recent years, oregano oil has garnered significant attention for its potential therapeutic role in addressing gastrointestinal conditions such as Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth (SIBO), Small Intestinal Fungal Overgrowth (SIFO), and the disruption of biofilms. These conditions, often associated with chronic digestive disturbances and are major contributors for leaky gut syndrome and the instalment of many different autoimmune diseases, have spurred interest in exploring natural remedies, and oregano oil's unique properties position it as a promising candidate for these applications [18].

Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth (SIBO):

SIBO refers to an excessive proliferation of bacteria in the small intestine, leading to a range of uncomfortable symptoms including bloating, gas, abdominal pain, and altered bowel habits [18]. Oregano oil's antimicrobial properties, attributed to its active compound carvacrol, have been demonstrated to combat the overgrowth of bacterial populations [12]. Carvacrol's ability to inhibit bacterial growth and disrupt the integrity of bacterial cell membranes may help rebalance the gut microbiota and alleviate symptoms associated with SIBO [12].

Small Intestinal Fungal Overgrowth (SIFO):

SIFO, on the other hand, entails an overgrowth of fungal species within the small intestine, particularly *Candida* species like *Candida albicans* [18]. Oregano oil's antifungal properties, also attributed to carvacrol, have shown promise in inhibiting the growth of *Candida* and other pathogenic fungi. By targeting the fungal burden within the small intestine, oregano oil may contribute to restoring microbial balance and relieving symptoms linked to SIFO [12].

Biofilm Disruption:

Biofilms represent complex communities of microorganisms encased in a protective matrix, often adhering to surfaces within the body. These biofilms play a significant role in the persistence of chronic infections, as they shield microorganisms from immune responses and conventional antimicrobial agents [18]. Oregano oil has gained recognition as a potent biofilm disruptor due to its ability to penetrate and dismantle the protective matrix, rendering the embedded microorganisms vulnerable to eradication. Carvacrol's multifaceted action, including disruption of biofilm architecture and interference with quorum sensing (communication among microorganisms), underscores its potential as a valuable tool in combating biofilm-associated infections [12].

Oregano oil's effectiveness as a biofilm disruptor is attributed to its ability to permeate the biofilm matrix and exert antimicrobial activity against the microorganisms nestled within. This unique property stems from carvacrol's lipophilic nature, allowing it to traverse the hydrophobic layers of the biofilm and directly target the enclosed pathogens. By doing so, oregano oil can enhance the efficacy of conventional antimicrobial agents, which often struggle to penetrate biofilms [19].

Incorporating oregano oil into clinical practice for managing SIBO, SIFO, and biofilm-related infections holds promise for patients seeking natural alternatives. However, it is important to note that individual responses may vary, and consulting a healthcare professional is crucial before introducing oregano oil as part of a treatment regimen. As research in this area continues to evolve, oregano oil's potential to offer multifaceted benefits in gastrointestinal health remains an intriguing avenue for exploration.

MATERIALS & METHODS

In this study, the effectiveness of oregano oil was evaluated against the following microorganisms: *Staphylococcus coagulase-negative*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus*.

The "Bauer-Kirby method" (disk diffusion method) was utilized in this study for assessing bacterial susceptibility or resistance specifically to oregano oil [20]. The experimental procedure involved samples obtained directly from patients and through the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC).

The preparation of a pure bacterial culture to be tested. The bacteria were obtained either from clinical samples or culture media and cultured to achieve a specific cell density.

Subsequently, the bacterial culture was evenly spread across the surface petri dish of a nutrient agar Mueller Hilton (MHA) medium and Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) medium plate for fungal specimens using a sterile cotton swab, resulting in the creation of a uniform bacterial and fungal lawn.

Standardized paper disks impregnated with a concentration of oregano oil were meticulously placed on the agar surface where each disk contained an approximate concentration of 122 mcg of oregano oil. The agar plates were then incubated at a controlled temperature, typically maintained at 35°C, for a predetermined period, typically 18 to 24 hours. During this incubation, the bacteria and fungus grew, forming visible bacterial and fungal lawns on their respective plates.

Following the incubation period, the plates were meticulously examined for zones of inhibition around each oregano oil-impregnated disk. Zones of inhibition appeared as areas of clearance or no bacterial or fungal growth surrounding the disks, indicating that the oregano oil had exerted inhibitory effects on bacterial growth.

The Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) or the European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) lacks standardized interpretive criteria for oregano oil. To interpret the results, the diameter of each inhibition zone was carefully measured using calipers or a ruler. The measurements were then compared to standardized interpretive criteria based on the Oregano Oil Antimicrobial Sensitivity Index (OOASI) established by the Saint Patrick Medical Sciences Institute (SPIMS) in the United States and the Clinical Laboratory RIDES in Bolivia [21]. The OOASI criteria classify the bacterial and fungal strains as very sensitive, sensitive, intermediate, or resistant to oregano oil based on the observed inhibition zones (Figure 1.0).

Oregano Oil Sensitivity Index (OOASI)	
Zone of Inhibition (mm)	Classification
0-5	Resistant
>5-10	Intermediate
>10-15	Sensitive
>15	Very Sensitive

SPIMS-RIDES Classification 2023

FIGURE 1.0
Oregano Oil Sensitivity Index Classification System. The OOASI method entails measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone formed around a disc containing oregano oil at a concentration of 122 mcg on an agar plate inoculated with a specific microbial strain.

Bacterial and Fungal Strains used:

In this study, the efficacy of oregano oil as a potential antimicrobial agent was rigorously investigated across a spectrum of clinically significant microbial strains. These strains, meticulously chosen to encompass a range of bacterial and fungal pathogens, included *Staphylococcus coagulase-negative*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Candida albicans*, and *Aspergillus*.

Staphylococcus coagulase-negative:

These bacteria, commonly found on the skin and mucous membranes, typically have low virulence. However, they can become opportunistic pathogens, particularly in healthcare-associated settings. *Staphylococcus coagulase-negative* strains are known to cause infections related to indwelling medical devices such as catheters and prosthetic implants. These infections can range from localized skin infections to more severe cases of septicemia in immunocompromised patients [22].

Staphylococcus aureus:

Staphylococcus aureus is a versatile pathogen known for its ability to cause a wide spectrum of infections. It is a leading cause of skin and soft tissue infections, including abscesses and cellulitis. More concerning are invasive infections like bloodstream infections (bacteremia), pneumonia, and endocarditis. *Staphylococcus aureus* produces toxins, such as exotoxins and enterotoxins, that contribute to its virulence and severity of infections [23].

Enterococcus:

Enterococci are commensal bacteria found in the human gut. Some strains, notably *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Enterococcus faecium*, have the potential to cause infections. They are often associated with urinary tract infections, intra-abdominal infections, and endocarditis. Enterococcal infections are particularly worrisome due to their ability to acquire resistance to multiple antibiotics, limiting treatment options [24].

Klebsiella pneumoniae:

Klebsiella pneumoniae is a member of the Enterobacteriaceae family. It is recognized for causing a range of infections, primarily in hospital settings. Infections attributed to *Klebsiella pneumoniae* include urinary tract infections, pneumonia, bloodstream infections, and infections of surgical sites. Some strains are notorious for producing extended-spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBLs) and carbapenemases, leading to antibiotic resistance [25].

Escherichia coli (E. coli):

E. coli is a diverse bacterium inhabiting the human gut. While most strains are harmless, pathogenic variants can lead to infections. Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC) causes traveler's diarrhea, enteropathogenic *E. coli* (EPEC) causes infantile diarrhea, and enterohemorrhagic *E. coli* (EHEC) is responsible for outbreaks of foodborne illness, potentially leading to hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS) with severe kidney complications [26].

Candida albicans:

Candida albicans is a fungus that typically resides in the oral cavity, gut, and genital tract. Overgrowth can lead to candidiasis, which includes oral thrush and vaginal infections. In immunocompromised individuals, *Candida* can cause invasive candidiasis, a serious bloodstream infection that can affect multiple organs and systems [27].

Aspergillus:

Aspergillus molds are prevalent in the environment and can cause a range of respiratory infections. Aspergillosis includes allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis (ABPA) in individuals with asthma, invasive aspergillosis in severely immunocompromised patients, and chronic pulmonary aspergillosis in those with underlying lung disease [28].

Central to this evaluation was the utilization of the Oregon Oil Antimicrobial Index (OOASI) [21]. The OOASI method entails measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone formed around a disc containing oregano oil at a concentration of 122 mcg on an agar plate inoculated with a specific microbial strain. This inhibition zone reflects the extent to which the oregano oil curtails the growth of the microorganism at the specified dose.

RESULTS

Staphylococcus coagulase-negative: The strain was obtained from a urine sample. The zone of inhibition observed on 06/24/2023 was of **12 mm** putting it in the sensitive range. Disc of 122 mcg were used. Zone of inhibition can be seen in **Figure A**.

FIGURE A: Zone of inhibition for *Staphylococcus coagulase-negative* with oregano oil: The strain was obtained from a urine sample. The zone of inhibition observed on 06/24/2023 was of 12 mm putting it in the sensitive range.

Staphylococcus aureus: The strain was obtained from a urine sample. The zone of inhibition observed on 07/14/2023 was of **9 mm** putting it in the sensitive range. Disc of 122 mcg were used. Zone of inhibition can be seen in **Figure B**.

FIGURE B: Zone of inhibition for *Staphylococcus aureus* with oregano oil: The strain was obtained from a urine sample. The zone of inhibition observed on 07/14/2023 was of 9 mm putting it in the sensitive range.

Enterococcus: The strain was obtained from the ATCC (American Type Culture Collection). The zone of inhibition observed on 07/14/2023 was of **8 mm** putting it in the Intermediate range. Disc of 122 mcg were used. Zone of inhibition can be seen in **Figure C**.

FIGURE C: Zone of inhibition for *Enterococcus* with oregano oil: The strain was obtained from a urine sample. The zone of inhibition observed on 07/14/2023 was of 8 mm putting it in the sensitive range.

Klebsiella pneumoniae: The strain was obtained from a urine sample. The zone of inhibition observed on 07/14/2023 was of **10 mm** putting it in the Intermediate range. Disc of 122 mcg were used. Zone of inhibition can be seen in **Figure D**.

FIGURE D: Zone of inhibition for *Klebsiella pneumoniae* with oregano oil: The strain was obtained from a urine sample. The zone of inhibition observed on 07/14/2023 was of **10 mm** putting it in the intermediate range.

Escherichia coli: The strain was obtained from a urine sample. The zone of inhibition observed on 06/20/2023 was of **10 mm** putting it in the Intermediate range. Disc of 122 mcg were used. Zone of inhibition can be seen in **Figure E**.

FIGURE E: Zone of inhibition for *E.coli* with oregano oil: The strain was obtained from a urine sample. The zone of inhibition observed on 06/20/2023 was of **10 mm** putting it in the intermediate range.

Candida albicans: The strain was obtained from a vaginal secretion. The zone of inhibition observed on 06/30/2023 was of **16 mm** putting it in the very sensitive range. Disc of 122 mcg were used. Zone of inhibition can be seen in **Figure F**.

FIGURE F: Zone of inhibition for *Candida albicans* with oregano oil: The strain was obtained from a vaginal secretion. The zone of inhibition observed on 06/30/2023 was of **12 mm** putting it in the very sensitive range.

Aspergillus : The strain was obtained from an ear secretion. The zone of inhibition observed on 07/17/2023 was of **25 mm** putting it in the every sensitive range. Disc of 122 mcg were used. Zone of inhibition can be seen in **Figure G**.

FIGURE G: Zone of inhibition for *Aspergillus* with oregano oil: The strain was obtained from an ear secretion. The zone of inhibition observed on 07/17/2023 was of **25 mm** putting it in the very sensitive range.

INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

In this study, the efficacy of oregano oil was evaluated against various strains, including *Staphylococcus coagulase-negative*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Candida albicans*, and *Aspergillus*.

To interpret the results, the zones of inhibition were classified into four categories based on their size: resistant (0-5 mm), intermediate (>5-10 mm), sensitive (>10-15 mm), and very sensitive (>15 mm). This classification system was based on the OOASI system (Figure 1.0), which allows for a clear determination of the susceptibility of each strain to oregano oil.

Among the strains tested, the zones of inhibition were as follows:

Oregano Oil 122 mcg /Disk	Resistant (R) 0-5 mm	Intermediate (I) >5-10mm	Sensitive (S) >10-15mm	Very Sensitive (VS) >15mm
<i>Staphylococcus coagulase-negative</i>			12	
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>		9		
<i>Enterococcus</i>		8		
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>		10		
<i>Escherichia coli</i>		10		
<i>Candida albicans</i>				16
<i>Aspergillus</i>				25

Interestingly, the zones of inhibition showed variability among the different strains. *Staphylococcus coagulase-negative* exhibited a 12 mm inhibition zone, suggesting sensitivity to oregano oil. *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Enterococcus* demonstrated zones of 9 mm and 8 mm, respectively, indicating a moderate level of susceptibility. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Escherichia coli*, both exhibited a 10 mm zone of inhibition, placing them in the intermediate category, signifying potential responsiveness.

The most striking findings were observed with *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus*. These fungal strains displayed inhibition zones of 16 mm and 25 mm, respectively, positioning them in the sensitive and very sensitive categories. This highlights the potential of oregano oil to exert strong antimicrobial effects against fungal infections.

Considering the strains' susceptibility and the cumulative data, a minimal broad-spectrum therapeutic dose was identified within the intermediate range, which displayed susceptibility across all strains. This indicates that at a concentration of 122 mcg, oregano oil demonstrated the ability to inhibit the growth of all tested strains, albeit to varying degrees.

CLINICAL CORRELATIONS & THERAPEUTIC APPLICATIONS

In line with our thorough investigation into the antimicrobial capabilities of oregano oil through in vitro experimentation, the convergence of clinical case studies conducted by Beltran et al. (SPIMS, 2023) offers a robust avenue to align laboratory discoveries with real-world patient encounters. Beltran et al.'s [29–32] clinical cases focus on a cohort of patients affected by diverse autoimmune diseases, including psoriasis, lupus, rheumatoid arthritis, and Crohn's disease. These studies probe into the effects of oregano oil as a supplementary intervention, particularly its use in addressing Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth (SIBO), Small Intestinal Fungal Overgrowth (SIFO), and biofilm-related challenges.

The clinical narratives provide insight into the application of herbal antimicrobials like oregano oil in mitigating gut dysbiosis across these autoimmune conditions. The decisive role of oregano oil as an antimicrobial agent for tackling persistent dysbiosis, SIBO, SIFO, or biofilm presence within the gastrointestinal tract emerges as a key driver in improving clinical outcomes. The mutual resonance between observed laboratory effects and tangible patient benefits reinforces the notion that herbal antimicrobials play a pivotal role in addressing complex microbial disruptions within the human body.

These clinical case studies underscore a pivotal correlation between empirical laboratory data and practical patient experiences, underscoring the therapeutic potential of oregano oil as an adjunct in autoimmune disease management. While these insights hold promise, the translation of laboratory findings into standardized therapeutic approaches warrants further substantiation through rigorous clinical trials.

DISCUSSION

The analysis presented earlier sheds a spotlight on the remarkable potential of oregano oil as a powerful antimicrobial agent, showcasing its effectiveness across a wide range of microbial strains. As we venture further into the intricate mechanisms that govern its actions, a more profound and comprehensive comprehension emerges, providing a roadmap for refining therapeutic strategies in the ongoing battle against antibiotic resistance.

The variations observed in inhibition zones among different bacterial strains offer a glimpse into the intricate interplay between oregano oil and bacterial physiology. The capacity of the compound to influence cell wall integrity and membrane stability suggests new avenues for exploration. Understanding the nuanced interactions between oregano oil and specific bacterial species has the potential to pave the way for precisely tailored treatment approaches, thus enhancing its efficacy even against the most resilient strains.

The exceptional sensitivity of *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus* to oregano oil ushers in a realm of possibilities for antifungal interventions. These distinct responses underscore the potential for highly targeted treatments in fungal infections.

Delving into the molecular underpinnings of this elevated susceptibility could lead to the development of focused therapies that minimize harm to beneficial microorganisms, thus optimizing treatment outcomes.

The concept of combining oregano oil with conventional antibiotics or other natural agents holds tantalizing promise. This collaborative approach capitalizes on the strengths of diverse antimicrobial agents, potentially revealing synergistic interactions that magnify efficacy while mitigating the risk of resistance emergence. These synergies have the potential to redefine treatment protocols, offering a robust defense against the challenges posed by multidrug-resistant pathogens.

Despite the invaluable insights gleaned from in vitro studies, bridging the gap between laboratory experiments and real-world clinical applications remains a critical endeavor. In vivo investigations play an indispensable role in evaluating the safety, pharmacokinetics, and effectiveness of oregano oil within living organisms. This essential step propels oregano oil beyond the confines of the laboratory and positions it as a tangible and viable therapeutic option for patients in need.

CONCLUSION

In summation, this study serves as a beacon illuminating the potential of oregano oil as a formidable antimicrobial contender. The nuanced variations in inhibition zones across diverse microbial strains underscore the imperative of tailored therapeutic regimens for distinct infections. Oregano oil's robust inhibitory prowess against bacterial and fungal strains positions it as a versatile therapeutic option with broad-spectrum implications.

The call for further investigation resounds resolutely. Mechanistic insights underlying oregano oil's efficacy demand elucidation, while calibrated dosages for intricate infections like SIBO, SIFO, and biofilm-associated challenges warrant meticulous establishment. The study unveils oregano oil as a promising biofilm disruptor, offering potential solutions for infections that defy conventional treatments. The curtain draws on this study with a promise, as oregano oil emerges as a protagonist in the relentless pursuit of innovative antimicrobial strategies against the backdrop of antibiotic resistance.

NOTES

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HUMAN ETHICS

Consent was obtained by all participants in this study.

REFERENCES

- Mortality, Length of Stay, and Healthcare Costs Associated With Multidrug-Resistant Bacterial Infections Among Elderly Hospitalized Patients in the United States. Richard E Nelson, David Hyun, Amanda Jezek, Matthew H Samore, *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, Volume 74, Issue 6. 2022:10701080. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciab696>
- Oregano, Overview of the Literature on Health Benefits, Singletary, Keith PhD: *Nutrition Today* 45(3): p 129-138, May. 2010. DOI: [10.1097/NT.0b013e3181dec789](https://doi.org/10.1097/NT.0b013e3181dec789)
- Oregano Benefits for Prostate Health, Dr. <https://www.bensnaturalhealth.com/blog/oregano-benefits/>.
- What are the health benefits of oregano?, Yvette Brazier, Updated on April 4, 2023 . <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/266259>.
- Antioxidant and Antimicrobial Activities of Essential Oils Obtained from Oregano (*Origanum vulgare* ssp . *hirtum*) by Using Different Extraction Methods, Sibel Karakaya et al, Published Online:26 May. 2011, 10:1089., <https://doi.org/10.1089/jmf.2010.0098>
- Antimicrobial activity of carvacrol related to its chemical structure. A Ben Arfa et al, *Lett Appl Microbiol*. 2006, 43:149-54. DOI: [10.1111/j.1472-765X.2006.01938.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-765X.2006.01938.x)
- Li, B., Zheng, K., Lu, J. et al.: Antibacterial characteristics of oregano essential oil and its mechanisms against *Escherichia coli* O157:H7. 16:2989-2998. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11694-022-01393-3>
- Feng, J., Lu, M., Wang, J. et al.: Dietary oregano essential oil supplementation improves intestinal functions and alters gut microbiota in late-phase laying hens. *J Animal Sci Biotechnol* 12. 72: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40104-021-00600-3>
- Scandorieiro S, et al (2016): Synergistic and Additive Effect of Oregano Essential Oil and Biological Silver Nanoparticles against Multidrug-Resistant Bacterial Strains. *Front. Microbiol.*, 05 November 2021, Sec: Food Microbiology, Volume 12. 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.741861>.
- Leyva-López, N.; Gutiérrez-Grijalva, E.P.; Vázquez-Olivo, G.; Heredia, J.B. Essential Oils of Oregano: Biological Activity beyond Their Antimicrobial Properties. *Molecules* 2017, 22, 989. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules22060989>
12. *Front. Microbiol.*, 05 November 2021, Sec: Food Microbiology, Volume 12. 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.741861>.
- Marinelli, L., Di Stefano, A. & Cacciatore, I: Carvacrol and its derivatives as antibacterial agents. *Phytochem Rev*. 17:903-921. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11101-018-9569-x>
- Carvacrol and thymol; Strong antimicrobial agents against resistant isolates . Mohammad Yousef Memarn et al. *Reviews in Medical Microbiology* 28(2): p 63-68, April. 2017, DOI: [10.1097/MRM.0000000000000100](https://doi.org/10.1097/MRM.0000000000000100)
- Pharmacological Properties and Molecular Mechanisms of Thymol: Prospects for Its Therapeutic Potential and Pharmaceutical Development, *Front. Pharmacol.*, 26 June. 2017, Mohamed Fizur Nagoor Meeran et al, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2017.00380>
- The Effects of Oregano Oil on Fungal Infections Associated with Metabolic Syndrome, TIMEA CLAUDIA GHITEA. <https://doi.org/10.37358/RC.20.1.7854>.
- Chemical Composition and Antifungal, Insecticidal and Repellent Activity of Essential Oils From *Origanum compactum* Benth. Used in the Mediterranean Diet, *Front. Plant Sci.*, 09 March. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2022.798259>
- Vitamin D Receptor Renewal Through Anti-inflammatory Diet (Another Contributing Factor for Vitamin D Resistance). *SPIMS* April. 2023, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7799798](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799798)
- The Natural Antimicrobial Carvacrol Inhibits Quorum Sensing in *Chromobacterium violaceum* and Reduces Bacterial Biofilm Formation at Sub-Lethal Concentrations, Sara A. Burt et al, *PLUS ONE*, Published: April 1. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0093414>
- In Vitro Activity of Essential Oils Against Gram-Positive and Gram-Negative Clinical Isolates, Including Carbapenem-Resistant Enterobacteriaceae. Jan E Patterson, *Open Forum Infectious Diseases*, Volume 6, Issue 12, December. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ofid/ofz502>
- Oregano Oil Antimicrobial Sensitivity Index (OOASI): A Basic Classification System for Assessing Oregano Oil's Efficacy Against Bacterial and Fungal Strains using 122 mcg Discs, Published *SPIMS* – August 2023, Beltran et al. DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.2.22819.43043](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22819.43043)
- Widerström, M., Wiström, J., Sjöstedt, A. et al.: Coagulase-negative staphylococci: update on the molecular epidemiology and clinical presentation, with a focus on *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Staphylococcus saprophyticus*. *Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis*. 31:7-20, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10096-011-1270-6>
- Pinchuk, I.V.; Beswick, E.J.; Reyes, V.E: Staphylococcal Enterotoxins. *Toxins*. 2010, 2:2177-2197. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins2082177>
- Sarathy, M.V., Balaji, S., Jagan Mohan Rao, T. (2020): Enterococcal Infections and Drug Resistance Mechanisms. In: Siddhardha, B., Dyavaiah, M., Syed, A. (eds) *Model Organisms for Microbial Pathogenesis, Biofilm Formation and Antimicrobial Drug Discovery*. Springer, Singapore; https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-1695-5_9
- Hawkey, J., Wyres, K.L., Judd, L.M. et al.: ESBL plasmids in *Klebsiella pneumoniae*: diversity, transmission and contribution to infection burden in the hospital setting. *Genome Med* 14. 97: (2024) <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13073-022-01103-0>
- CDC-*Escherichia coli*, Diarrheagenic, CDC Yellow Book 2024, *Travel-Associated Infections & Diseases*, Jennifer Collins, <https://wwwnc.cdc.gov/travel/yellowbook/2024/infections-diseases/escherichia-colidiarrheagenic>.
- CDC -Antimicrobial Resistance in *Candida*, [Antimicrobial Resistance in Candida | Fungal Diseases | CDC](https://www.cdc.gov/fungal/diseases/candida/antimicrobial-resistance-in-candida/)
- CDC - Aspergillosis [About Aspergillosis, Aspergillosis, Types of Fungal Diseases, Fungal Diseases, CDC](https://www.cdc.gov/fungal/diseases/aspergillosis/)

REFERENCES

29. Clinical Case Report: High Dose Vitamin D Therapy & Anti-inflammatory Diet (Systemic Lupus 13 of 14 Erythematosus & Alopecia Areata). April. 2023, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7800324](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7800324)
30. Clinical Case Report: High Dose Vitamin D Therapy & Anti-inflammatory Diet (Rheumatoid Arthritis) . March. 2023, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7799873](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799873)
31. Clinical Case Report: High Dose Vitamin D Therapy & Anti-inflammatory Diet (Psoriasis Vulgaris) . March. 2023, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7799594](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799594)
32. Clinical Case Report: High Dose Vitamin D Therapy & Anti-inflammatory Diet (Crohn's Disease) . April. 2023, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7812369](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7812369)